

Effectiveness of Pharmacist-Assisted SBIRT in Identifying Problematic Alcohol Use in Hospitalized Patients

T. Sravanti¹, A. Bhagyasri¹, Girija Pashikanti^{1*}, B. Thrilok Chander², B. S. Sharvana Bhava¹, V. Sneha Priya¹

¹Department of Clinical Pharmacy, Pharm D, MGM Hospital, Vaagdevi College of Pharmacy, Telangana, India,

²Department of General Medicine, MGM Hospital, Warangal, Telangana, India

ABSTRACT

Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD) poses a significant public health burden. Screening, Brief Intervention, and Referral to Treatment (SBIRT) is an evidence-based model for addressing problematic substance use. Pharmacists, due to their accessibility, are uniquely positioned to implement SBIRT in tertiary care settings. Objective: This study aimed to evaluate the feasibility and impact of pharmacist-led SBIRT in identifying and addressing the risk of AUD in a tertiary care teaching hospital. Methods: A prospective, observational, and interventional study was conducted among 486 patients with a history of alcohol consumption in a general medicine ward. Patients underwent pharmacist-led SBIRT, utilizing the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) for screening, followed by brief interventions and referral to treatment as appropriate. Patients were followed up across three visits (baseline, post-intervention, and follow-up). Results: At baseline (Visit 1), 54.5% of patients were classified as dependent users. Following SBIRT intervention, this proportion significantly reduced to 12.8% at Visit 3 (follow-up), with a notable increase in low-risk patients from 0.4% to 17.5%. The percentage of risky users increased from 17.1% to 52.7%, suggesting a shift towards lower-risk categories. Conclusion: Pharmacist-led SBIRT is feasible and effective in significantly reducing alcohol dependence among patients in a tertiary care teaching hospital, demonstrating the critical role pharmacists can play in early identification and intervention for AUD.

Keywords: Alcohol Dependence, Alcohol Use Disorder, Pharmacist's Role, Tertiary Care Hospital, Brief Intervention, Referral to Treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD) is a chronic, relapsing condition characterized by compulsive alcohol consumption, impaired control over drinking, and the emergence of negative emotional states during withdrawal. Globally, AUD significantly contributes to morbidity and mortality, affecting multiple organ systems including the central nervous system (CNS), cardiovascular system (CVS), and digestive system, while also increasing the risk of various cancers and psychiatric disorders¹⁻⁹. Despite its widespread prevalence, access to effective treatment remains limited due to stigma, inadequate screening practices, and socioeconomic barriers.

Alcohol consumption is deeply ingrained in many cultures worldwide, often associated with social and ceremonial activities. While low-to-moderate alcohol intake may facilitate socialization by reducing anxiety and disinhibiting social behaviors, excessive consumption leads to a broad spectrum of adverse health outcomes. The National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism (NIAAA) defines heavy drinking as more than four drinks per day or 14 drinks per week for men, and more than three drinks per day or seven drinks per week for women. Approximately one in four heavy drinkers develop alcohol-related problems, including dependence¹. Alcohol is a causal factor in over 30 medical conditions, ranging from infectious diseases and neuropsychiatric disorders to

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

cardiovascular disease and various cancers². The societal and individual costs of alcohol misuse underscore the urgent need for effective prevention and treatment strategies. The neurobiology of addiction involves complex interactions among brain regions responsible for motivation, reward, and executive function. The addiction cycle encompasses three stages: preoccupation and anticipation, binge and intoxication, and withdrawal with negative affect, each mediated by distinct neurocircuits^{3,4}. The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5), integrates previous categorizations of alcohol abuse and dependence into a single disorder characterized by varying severity levels⁵. Susceptibility to AUD is influenced by genetic predisposition, age at onset, environmental stressors, and socioeconomic status. Chronic alcohol use disrupts sleep, impairs cognitive function, and predisposes individuals to psychiatric comorbidities⁶⁻¹². Beyond the CNS, alcohol exerts detrimental effects on the cardiovascular system, contributing to hypertension, arrhythmias, cardiomyopathy, and cerebrovascular accidents¹³⁻¹⁵. Alcohol-induced liver injury remains a major global health concern, with alcoholic liver disease (ALD) encompassing a spectrum from steatosis to cirrhosis and liver failure¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Furthermore, alcohol consumption is linked to increased risks of cancers of the breast, colon, liver, esophagus, and other sites, through mechanisms involving acetaldehyde toxicity, oxidative stress, and DNA methylation alterations¹⁹⁻²¹. Alcohol also impairs immune function and disrupts gastrointestinal microbiota, exacerbating systemic inflammation and disease susceptibility²²⁻²³. Treatment options for AUD encompass both pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches. Despite the high prevalence of AUD and its associated mortality, only a minority of affected individuals receive treatment, hindered by stigma, insufficient screening, and limited access²⁴⁻²⁸. Psychological interventions such as motivational interviewing, cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), and support groups like Alcoholics Anonymous (AA) form foundational components of AUD management²⁹⁻³⁴. Pharmacotherapies approved by the FDA, including disulfiram, naltrexone, and acamprosate, offer additional tools to reduce craving and prevent relapse but remain underutilized in clinical practice³⁵⁻⁴⁴.

Screening, Brief Intervention, and Referral to Treatment (SBIRT) is an integrated, evidence-based public health approach designed to identify and address risky substance use early. SBIRT consists of systematic screening to detect at-risk individuals, brief motivational interventions tailored to risk level, and referral to specialized treatment when indicated⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. Pharmacists, due to their accessibility, medication expertise, and frequent patient contact, are uniquely positioned to implement SBIRT within hospital settings, bridging gaps in the continuum of care for individuals with AUD⁵⁰. This study evaluates the feasibility and effectiveness of pharmacist-led SBIRT in a tertiary care teaching hospital, comparing intervention outcomes with AUDIT risk scores to assess impact on alcohol use severity. Alcohol consumption is a global public health issue, and its misuse is a major contributor to morbidity and mortality. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), alcohol is linked to a wide range of diseases, both acute and chronic, which significantly burden healthcare systems. To date, there are several studies that have implemented screening tools to assess alcohol use within the patient population presenting to tertiary care hospital settings that implemented pharmacist led strategies to support alcohol use cessation. Additionally, there have been several surveys working groups and advisory boards constructed to understand the potential feasibility of implementing SBIRT protocols in the community pharmacy setting, as well as understanding the perceived barrier to implementation. However, this is the first study that has attempted to implement SBIRT protocols, evaluating comprehensive alcohol use in tertiary hospital settings, and comparing SBIRT screening outcomes with AUDIT based risk assessment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This prospective, observational, and interventional study was conducted at Mahatma Gandhi Memorial (MGM) Hospital, Warangal, Telangana. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (Approval No. KIEC-2025/Pharm D-2020/Project-07). Informed consent was secured from all participants in their local language.

Participants

A total of 486 adult patients (aged ≥ 18 years) diagnosed with alcohol-related disorders were recruited from the general medicine ward. Inclusion criteria encompassed clinical or ICD-10 diagnosis of alcohol-related disorders, including AUD, alcoholic liver disease, alcohol-induced psychiatric conditions, and alcohol withdrawal syndrome. Patients with comorbidities such as cardiovascular or psychiatric disorders were included to assess the interplay of these conditions. Exclusion criteria were patients under 18, those admitted for non-alcohol-related conditions, severe cognitive impairment, inability or unwillingness to consent, and patients in remission from AUD.

SBIRT PROTOCOL

SBIRT was implemented in three phases:

Screening: The Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT), a validated 10-item WHO

questionnaire, was used to categorize patients into risk groups: low risk (0–7), hazardous (8–15), harmful (16–19), and likely dependence (20–40) [Table 1]. Screening was conducted respectfully, with patient permission and without confrontation.

Brief Intervention: Pharmacists employed motivational interviewing techniques, including open-ended questions, affirmations, and reflective listening, to provide personalized feedback based on AUDIT scores. Interventions emphasized empathy, client autonomy, and goal setting. Advice was tailored to risk level: reinforcing healthy choices for low-risk patients, brief advice for moderate risk, and discussion of treatment needs for high-risk individuals⁵⁰. **Referral to Treatment:** Patients identified with high-risk or dependent use were referred to specialized outpatient treatment facilities. Follow-up visits were scheduled at 1–3 months for low/moderate risk patients and sooner for high-risk patients to monitor progress.

Table 1: AUDIT Scale

S.NO	Questions	0	1	2	3	4
01	How often do you have a drink containing alcohol?	Never	Monthly or less	2 to 4 times a month	2 to 3 times a week	4 or more times a week
02	How many drinks containing alcohol do you have on a typical day when you are drinking?	1 or 2	3 or 4	5 or 6	7 to 8	10 or more
03	How often do you have 6 or more drinks on one occasion?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily
04	How often during the last year have you found that you were not able to stop drinking once you had started?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily
05	How often during the last year have you failed to do what was normally expected of you because of drinking?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily
06	How often during the last year have you needed a first drink in the morning to get yourself going after a heavy drinking session?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily
07	How often during the last year have you had a feeling of guilt or remorse after drinking?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily
08	How often during the last year have you been unable to remember what happened the night before because of your drinking?	Never	Less than monthly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily or almost daily

09	Have you or someone else been injured because of your drinking?	No		Yes, but not in the last year		Yes, during the last year
10	Has a relative, friend, doctor or other healthcare worker been concerned about your drinking or suggested you cut down?	No		Yes, but not in the last year		Yes, during the last year

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Demographic data, clinical diagnoses, and AUDIT scores at baseline, post-intervention, and follow-up visits were collected. Statistical analyses using Microsoft Excel and GraphPad Prism 9.0 included

descriptive statistics and two-way ANOVA to evaluate changes in AUDIT risk categories over time, with significance set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

RESULTS

Table 2: AUD patients Percentage in Various age groups

Age Group	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
20-30	43	8.85
30-40	130	26.75
40-50	126	25.93
50-60	94	19.35
60-70	82	16.87
70-80	10	2.06
80-90	1	0.21

Table 3: History of Alcohol use percentage

Years	No. of Patients	Percentage (%)
1 – 5	109	22.43
5 – 10	128	26.34
10 – 15	104	21.40
15 – 20	97	19.96
20+	48	9.88

Table 4: Socio Economic Factors in Various Patients

Educated	119	24.48%
Uneducated	367	75.52%
Married	427	87.62%
Unmarried	69	12.38%

Table 5: AUD Patients Diagnosed with Various Diseases and their percentage

S.NO	DIAGNOSIS	NO. OF PATIENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	AH (alcoholic hepatitis)	18	4.23
2	AKI (acute kidney injury)	15	3.53
3	ALD (alcoholic liver disease)	33	7.76
4	AP (acute pancreatitis)	86	20.18
5	AWS (alcoholic withdrawal syndrome)	106	24.91
6	CAD (coronary artery disease)	17	3.99
7	CKD (chronic kidney disease)	17	3.99

8	COL (cirrhosis of liver)	10	2.35
9	CVA (Cerebro vascular accident)	26	6.10
10	DCMP (dilated cardiomyopathy)	16	3.76
11	DCOL (Degenerative Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease)	28	6.57
12	Jaundice	12	2.82
13	LRTI lower respiratory tract infection)	13	3.05
14	LVD (left ventricular dysfunction)	8	1.88
15	MBD (mental and behavioural disorder)	40	9.39
16	Seizures	19	4.46
17	UTI (urinary tract infection)	12	2.82
18	VH (viral hepatitis)	10	2.35

Table 6: Comparison between the Results of SBIRT screening and AUDIT risk scores

AUDIT Risk Category	Visit 1 (Before SBIRT)	Visit 2 (Post SBIRT)	Visit 3 (Follow up)
Low Risk (0-7)	2± 1.4	26±2.3	85±3.6
Risky Use (8-15)	83±5.2	196±6.5	256±7.0
Harmful use (16-40)	136±6.8	146±5.9	83±6.1
Dependent use (20-40)	265±7.1	118±6.2	62±5.8

The values are expressed as mean ± standard deviation, (n=486), *p<0.05 as comparison made between each column mean

Table 7: Percentage changes in AUDIT risk scores (n=486)

AUDIT Risk Category	Visit 1 (%)	Visit 2(%)	Visit 3(%)
Low Risk (0-7)	0.4	5.3	17.5
Risky Use (8-15)	17.1	40.3	52.7
Harmful use (16-40)	28.0	30.0	17.1
Dependent use (20-40)	54.5	24.3	12.8

Values are in percentages during 3 visits

The study involved 486 patients diagnosed with alcohol-related disorders admitted to a tertiary care teaching hospital. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority of patients were middle-aged adults between 30 and 50 years (52.68%), predominantly uneducated (75.52%), and mostly married (87.62%). The duration of alcohol use varied, with the largest groups having consumed alcohol for 1–5 years (22.43%) and 5–10 years (26.34%). [Table 2-4] Clinically, the most common diagnoses among these patients were Alcoholic Withdrawal Syndrome (24.91%), Acute Pancreatitis (20.18%), and Alcoholic Liver Disease (7.76%), reflecting the substantial health burden of alcohol misuse. [Table 5] The core outcome measure was the change in Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test (AUDIT) risk categories over three visits: baseline (Visit 1), post-SBIRT intervention (Visit 2), and follow-up (Visit 3). [Table 6&7]

At baseline (Visit 1):

54.5% of patients were classified as dependent use (AUDIT score 20–40). 28.0% were in the harmful use category (16–19). 17.1% were in risky use (8–15). Only 0.4% were low risk (0–7).

Post-intervention (Visit 2):

Dependent use decreased significantly to 24.3%. Risky use increased to 40.3%. Harmful use slightly increased to 30%. Low risk rose modestly to 5.3%.

At follow-up (Visit 3):

Dependent use further declined to 12.8%, indicating sustained reduction in severe misuse. Risky use increased to 52.7%, suggesting many patients transitioned from dependence to lower-risk consumption. Low risk increased substantially to 17.5%. Harmful use decreased to 17.1%. These shifts

indicate that the SBIRT intervention effectively reduced the proportion of patients with severe alcohol dependence while increasing those in lower-risk categories.

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates that pharmacist-led SBIRT is a feasible and effective intervention in a tertiary care hospital setting for managing Alcohol Use Disorder (AUD). Pharmacists, due to their accessibility and expertise, can successfully conduct screening, deliver brief interventions, and facilitate referrals to specialized treatment.

Reduction in Dependent Use: The most notable change was the significant decrease in patients classified as dependent use, from 54.5% at baseline to 12.8% at follow-up. This suggests that SBIRT's brief interventions and referrals played a critical role in mitigating severe alcohol misuse.

Increase in Risky Use: The rise in the risky use category (from 17.1% to 52.7%) indicates that many patients reduced their alcohol consumption from dependence to lower-risk levels. This shift reflects harm reduction success, where patients move from severe misuse to safer drinking patterns.

Stable Harmful Use Group: The harmful use category showed only a modest reduction (28% to 17.1%), highlighting that SBIRT alone may not be sufficient for all patients. Those in this group may require more intensive or prolonged interventions beyond brief counseling.

Low Risk Increase: The increase in low-risk patients (0.4% to 17.5%) suggests that a subset of patients achieved near-abstinence or safe drinking behaviors after intervention.

Role of Pharmacists: Pharmacists' frequent interactions with patients during hospital stays and medication management make them well-suited to integrate SBIRT into clinical practice. Their medication expertise also supports patient education and coordination with other healthcare providers. The study's acceptance by patients and healthcare teams supports expanding pharmacists' roles in public health interventions targeting AUD.

Barriers and Considerations: Time constraints, limited training, and unclear role definitions were identified as barriers to full implementation of SBIRT by pharmacists. Institutional support and targeted training programs are necessary to overcome these challenges. The study's single-center design and short follow-up period limit the ability to assess long-term outcomes. Future multi-center studies with extended follow-up are needed to confirm sustained benefits and optimize intervention protocols.

Implications: Pharmacist-led SBIRT can reduce the burden of alcohol dependence in hospital settings and potentially decrease alcohol-related complications, easing pressure on emergency and inpatient services. The persistent presence of risky and harmful use categories at follow-up suggests ongoing monitoring and possibly stepped-up interventions are required for these patients. Integration of SBIRT into pharmacy education and continuing professional development could enhance effectiveness and expand the reach of AUD interventions.

CONCLUSION

Pharmacist-led SBIRT is a feasible and effective approach for identifying and reducing AUD severity in tertiary care hospital patients. Combining SBIRT with AUDIT scoring enhances risk stratification and targeting of interventions. The observed shift from dependent to lower-risk drinking categories supports SBIRT as a valuable public health tool. Further research should focus on long-term efficacy and tailored interventions for harmful and risky use populations to optimize AUD management.

REFERENCES

1. Clapp P, Wackernah R, Minnick M. Alcohol use disorder: pathophysiology, effects, and pharmacologic options for treatment. *Substance Abuse and Rehabilitation*. 2014;5(5):1–12.
2. Varghese J, Dakhode S. Effects of Alcohol Consumption on Various Systems of the Human Body: A Systematic Review. *Cureus*. 2022;14(10).
3. Yang W, Singla R, Maheshwari O, Fontaine CJ, Gil-Mohapel J. Alcohol Use Disorder: Neurobiology and Therapeutics. *Biomedicines*. 2022;10(5).

4. American Psychological Association. Understanding alcohol use disorders and their treatment. 2020.
5. Koob GF, Moal ML. Drug abuse: hedonic homeostatic dysregulation. *Science*. 1997;278(5335):52-8.
6. Brower KJ, Hall JM. Effects of age and alcoholism on sleep: a controlled study. *Journal of Studies on Alcohol*. 2001;62(3):335-43.
7. World Health Organization. Global Status Report on Alcohol and Health. 2014.
8. Hearne R, Connolly A, Sheehan J. Alcohol abuse: prevalence and detection in a general hospital. *J R Soc Med*. 2002;95(2):84-7.
9. Schuckit MA. Alcohol-use disorders. *The Lancet*. 2009;373(9662):492-501.
10. Harrison NL, Skelly MJ, Grosserode EK, Lowes DC, Zeric T, Phister S, Salling MC. Effects of acute alcohol on excitability in the CNS. *Neuropharmacology*. 2017;122:36-45.
11. Castaneda R, Sussman N, Westreich L, Levy R, O'Malley M. A review of the effects of moderate alcohol intake on the treatment of anxiety and mood disorders. *J Clin Psychiatry*. 1996;57(5):207-12.
12. Chan AW. Alcoholism and epilepsy. *Epilepsia*. 1985;26(4):323-33.
13. Day E, Rudd JH. Alcohol use disorders and the heart. *Addiction*. 2019;114(9):1670-8.
14. Faintuch JJ. Repercussions cardiovasculares do alcoolismo. *Rev Hosp Clin Fac Med Univ Sao Paulo*. 1995;76:76-9.
15. Klatsky AL. Alcohol and hypertension. *Clin Chim Acta*. 1996;246(1-2):91-105.
16. O'Shea RS, Dasarathy S, McCullough AJ, Practice Guideline Committee of the American Association for the Study of Liver Diseases and the Practice Parameters Committee of the American College of Gastroenterology. Alcoholic liver disease. *Hepatology*. 2010;51(1):307-28.
17. Lackner C, Tiniakos D. Fibrosis and alcohol-related liver disease. *J Hepatol*. 2019;70(2):294-304.
18. Roerecke M, Vafaei A, Hasan OS, et al. Alcohol consumption and risk of liver cirrhosis: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Am J Gastroenterol*. 2019;114(10):1574-86.
19. Taneri PE, Kiefe-de Jong JC, Bramer WM, et al. Association of alcohol consumption with the onset of natural menopause: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Hum Reprod Update*. 2016;22(4):516-28.
20. Na HK, Lee JY. Molecular basis of alcohol-related gastric and colon cancer. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2017;18(6):1116.
21. Boffetta P, Hashibe M. Alcohol and cancer. *Lancet Oncol*. 2006;7(2):149-56.
22. Purohit V, Khalsa J, Serrano J. Mechanisms of alcohol-associated cancers: introduction and summary of the symposium. *Alcohol*. 2005 Apr 1;35(3):155-60.
23. Engen PA, Green SJ, Voigt RM, Forsyth CB, Keshavarzian A. The gastrointestinal microbiome: alcohol effects on the composition of intestinal microbiota. *Alcohol Res*. 2015;37(2):223-36.
24. World Health Organization. Global Status Report on Alcohol and Health. 2014. World Health Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2014; 1–392
25. Park-Lee E, Lipari RN, Hedden SL, Kroutil LA, Porter JD. Receipt of services for substance use and mental health issues among adults: Results from the 2016 National Survey on Drug Use and Health.
26. McCrady BS, Epstein EE, Fokas KF. Treatment interventions for women with alcohol use disorder. *Alcohol Res*. 2020;40(2).
27. Hasin DS, Grant BF. Major depression in former drinkers: association with past alcohol dependence. *Arch Gen Psychiatry*. 2002;59(9):794-800.
28. Smedslund G, Berg RC, Hammerstrøm KT, et al. Motivational interviewing for substance abuse. *Campbell Systematic Reviews*. 2011;7(1):1-26.
29. Weiss RD, O'Malley SS, Hosking JD, et al. Do patients with alcohol dependence respond to placebo? Results from the COMBINE Study. *J Stud Alcohol Drugs*. 2008;69(6):878-84.
30. McHugh RK, Hearon BA, Otto MW. Cognitive-behavioral therapy for substance use disorders. *Psychiatr Clin North Am*. 2010;33(3):511-25.
31. Kelly JF, Humphreys K, Ferri M. Alcoholics Anonymous and other 12-step programs for alcohol use disorder. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2020;(3):CD012880.

32. Ambrogne JA. Reduced-risk drinking as a treatment goal: what clinicians need to know. *J Subst Abuse Treat.* 2002;22(1):45-53.
33. Gossop M, Stewart D, Marsden J. Attendance at Narcotics Anonymous and Alcoholics Anonymous meetings, frequency of attendance and substance use outcomes after residential treatment for drug dependence: a 5-year follow-up study. *Addiction.* 2008;103(1):119-25.
34. Wang M, Zhang X, Ma LJ, et al. Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids ameliorate ethanol-induced adipose hyperlipolysis: A mechanism for hepatoprotective effect against alcoholic liver disease. *Biochim Biophys Acta Mol Basis Dis.* 2017;1863(12):3190-201.
35. Diana M, Bolloni C, Antonelli M, et al. Repetitive transcranial magnetic stimulation: Re-wiring the alcoholic human brain. *Alcohol.* 2019;74:113-24.
36. Mark TL, Kassed CA, Vandivort-Warren R, Levit KR, Kranzler HR. Alcohol and opioid dependence medications: prescription trends, overall and by physician specialty. *Drug Alcohol Depend.* 2009;99(1-3):345-9.
37. Suh JJ, Pettinati HM, Kampman KM, O'Brien CP. The status of disulfiram: a half of a century later. *J Clin Psychopharmacol.* 2006;26(3):290-302.
38. Ulrichsen J, Nielsen MK, Ulrichsen M. Disulfiram in severe alcoholism—An open controlled study. *Nord J Psychiatry.* 2010;64(6):356-62.
39. Skinner MD, Lahmek P, Pham H, Aubin HJ. Disulfiram efficacy in the treatment of alcohol dependence: a meta-analysis. *PLoS One.* 2014;9(2):e87366.
40. Alharbi FF, el-Guebaly N. The relative safety of disulfiram. *Addict Disord Their Treat.* 2013;12(3):140-7.
41. Donoghue K, Elzerbi C, Saunders R, Whittington C, Pilling S, Drummond C. The efficacy of acamprosate and naltrexone in the treatment of alcohol dependence, Europe versus the rest of the world: a meta-analysis. *Addiction.* 2015;110(6):920-30.
42. Rösner S, Hackl-Herrwerth A, Leucht S, Lehert P, Vecchi S, Soyka M. Acamprosate for alcohol dependence. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev.* 2010;(9):CD004332.
43. Anton RF, Pettinati H, Zweben A, et al. A multi-site dose ranging study of nalmefene in the treatment of alcohol dependence. *J Clin Psychopharmacol.* 2004;24(4):421-8.
44. Pierce M, Sutterland A, Beraha EM, Morley K, van den Brink W. Efficacy, tolerability, and safety of low-dose and high-dose baclofen in the treatment of alcohol dependence: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Eur Neuropsychopharmacol.* 2018;28(7):795-806.
45. Leung JG, Hall-Flavin D, Nelson S, Schmidt KA, Schak KM. The role of gabapentin in the management of alcohol withdrawal and dependence. *Ann Pharmacother.* 2015;49(8):897-906.
46. White HS, Brown SD, Woodhead JH, Skeen GA, Wolf HH. Topiramate enhances GABA-mediated chloride flux and GABA-evoked chloride currents in murine brain neurons and increases seizure threshold. *Epilepsy Res.* 1997;28(3):167-79.
47. Mula M, Cavanna AE, Monaco F. Psychopharmacology of topiramate: from epilepsy to bipolar disorder. *Neuropsychiatr Dis Treat.* 2006;2(4):475-89.
48. Soyka M, Müller CA. Pharmacotherapy of alcoholism—an update on approved and off-label medications. *Expert Opin Pharmacother.* 2017;18(12):1187-99.
49. Shonesy BC, Williams D, Simmons D, Dorval E, Gitlow S, Gustin RM. Screening, Brief Intervention, and Referral to Treatment in a Retail Pharmacy Setting. *J Addict Med.* 2019;13(5):403-7.
50. National Institute on Alcohol Abuse and Alcoholism. Helping patients who drink too much: A clinician's guide. 2005.

HOW TO CITE: T. Sravanti, A. Bhagyasri, Girija Pashikanti*, B. Thrilok Chander, B. S. Sharvana Bhava, V. Sneha Priya, Effectiveness of Pharmacist-Assisted SBIRT in Identifying Problematic Alcohol Use in Hospitalized Patients *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 36-43. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17775742>

